

Post-Lecture Survey

- Which interface did you use?
- Which lecture did you just finish?
- How new was the lecture material to you? [7-point Likert]

For each question below, rate how much you agree or disagree. [7-point Likert]

- (Keeping up with the lecture) I was able to keep up with the lecture without falling behind
- (Engagement) I felt engaged with the lecture material while using this interface
- (Ease of Use) It was easy to take notes during the session
- (Learning) The way I took notes with this interface helped me learn
- (Quality of Notes) I think the notes I took would be useful if I revisited them later
- (Class Exercise) When the instructor asked you to solve a problem by writing your own code, it was easy to get started
- (Exploration and Tinkering) During the session, I felt like I could easily try out my own version of the code

In-Person Closing Survey

- How was what you did today different from what you would normally do in lectures that involve live coding? [text response]
- Did you prefer using one interface over the other? [7-point Likert]
- Please explain your reasoning for the above question, i.e., why do you prefer one interface over the other (or not)? [text response]
- Do you have any suggestions for us about how to improve your preferred interface? [text response]
- Do you have any other suggestions or anything else you'd like to tell us? [text response]

Addendum to Take-Home Quizzes

- (Notes usage) I consulted my notes frequently during the quiz [7-point Likert]
- (Notes quality) I feel satisfied with the quality of my notes [7-point Likert]

Final Survey (After Take-Home Quizzes)

- Now that time has passed, please indicate if you prefer one interface to the other. [7-point Likert]
- Based on your experience taking the quizzes, did you feel that one set of notes was more effective than the other? Please explain your reasoning. [text response]
- Do you have any other thoughts or suggestions? Is there anything else you'd like to tell us? [text response]